

Reproduction and Modernization of Physics-Informed Neural Networks in TensorFlow 2: A Case Study with the Schrödinger Equation

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Abstract

Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) constitute a promising approach for solving partial differential equations (PDEs) by incorporating physical laws into the neural network training process. Despite the positive results reported in the literature, the practical application of PINNs to highly nonlinear PDEs still presents relevant challenges. This work presents a reproduction of the seminal article by Raissi et al., initially implemented in TensorFlow 1.15, followed by a modernization of the pipeline to TensorFlow 2.x/Keras. The focus of the study is the empirical analysis of PINN behavior when solving the nonlinear Schrödinger equation, with special attention to training stability and the shape of the learned solutions. The experiments indicate that, under the classical PINN configuration, the model systematically converges to approximately constant solutions that minimize the PDE residual through the cancellation of spatial and temporal derivatives, but fail to reproduce the physical structure of the exact solution. This phenomenon, referred to as solution collapse, is analyzed through spatio-temporal visualizations and temporal slices of the solution. In addition, an exploratory study is conducted comparing the traditional MLP architecture with Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KAN) as the backbone of the PINN. Although neither architecture was able to reconstruct the exact solution under the adopted protocol, qualitative differences were observed in the type of degenerate solution learned, highlighting the impact of architectural inductive bias on PINN behavior. The results reinforce that solution collapse persists even after

the modernization of the computational framework, indicating that it is an intrinsic methodological limitation of classical PINNs, and show that architectural choices influence the type of degenerate solution to which training converges.

Keywords: Physics-Informed Neural Networks; TensorFlow 2; Schrödinger Equation; Scientific Reproduction; Architectural Analysis.

1 Introduction

Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) have become established as a deep learning approach for solving partial differential equations (PDEs) by incorporating the physical laws of the problem through equation residuals in the loss function. Unlike purely data-driven methods, PINNs exploit prior knowledge about the physics of the system, including initial and boundary conditions, making them an alternative for scenarios with scarce, incomplete, or noisy data [4].

The work of Maziar Raissi, Paris Perdikaris, and George Em Karniadakis formally introduced the PINN framework and established a series of benchmark problems widely adopted by the community, including the Burgers, Schrödinger, Allen–Cahn, and Navier–Stokes equations. In these studies, the authors reported relative errors on the order of 10^{-3} using Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) architectures with `tanh` activation and a hybrid optimization protocol based on Adam followed by L-BFGS-B [4].

Despite the impact of these results, a large portion of the original implementations was developed in TensorFlow 1.x, using static graphs and explicit sessions, which imposes relevant practical difficulties in terms of maintenance, extensibility, and reproducibility in the contemporary deep learning ecosystem, now largely based on TensorFlow 2.x and Keras. Later works have emphasized that reproducibility and software engineering quality are determining factors for the adoption of scientific machine learning methods [1].

In addition, more recent studies have pointed out that classical PINNs may present practical limitations when dealing with highly nonlinear, oscillatory, or stiff PDEs, such as the nonlinear Schrödinger equation. Reported issues include training instabilities, sensitivity to hyperparameter choices, and convergence to degenerate or physically trivial solutions that minimize the PDE residual but do not reproduce the correct physical solution [5, 2].

At the same time, alternative neural architectures have been investigated with the aim of increasing functional expressiveness and reducing the number

of parameters required to approximate complex functions. In this context, Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs) stand out, as they are grounded in the Kolmogorov–Arnold representation theorem, which allows multivariate functions to be represented as compositions of univariate functions. Recent results indicate that KANs may provide greater parameter efficiency and a reduced inductive bias toward overly smooth functions when compared to traditional MLPs [3].

Against this background, this work proposes a reproduction and modernization of the classical PINN pipeline, with the nonlinear Schrödinger equation as the main case study, chosen as a representative example of highly nonlinear and oscillatory PDEs. Specifically, the following aspects are investigated: (i) reproduction of the original TensorFlow 1.15 pipeline, focusing on the numerical validation of the method; (ii) full refactoring into TensorFlow 2.x/Keras, evaluating whether modernization changes the training behavior; and (iii) an exploratory analysis of the impact of architectural inductive bias by replacing the traditional MLP with Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs). Although the methodological design considers other classical PINN benchmark problems for implementation consistency checks, the detailed experimental analysis is focused exclusively on the nonlinear Schrödinger equation.

Unlike works focused exclusively on numerical performance, this study emphasizes the empirical analysis of the practical limitations of PINNs, investigating how architectural and implementation choices influence the type of solution to which training converges. In doing so, the work contributes to a broader understanding of the use of PINNs in complex PDEs, reinforcing the importance of reproducibility, modern engineering, and failure analysis in the development of machine learning methods for physical problems.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the materials and methods adopted. Section 3 presents the experimental results with a focus on the Schrödinger equation. Section 4 critically discusses the findings. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the conclusions and future research directions.

2 Materials and Methods

The methodology of this work is based on a reproduction of the Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) method proposed by Raissi et al., followed by its modernization to a contemporary computational environment and an exploratory analysis of the architectural impact of replacing the tra-

ditional MLP backbone with Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs). The methodological focus is not limited to obtaining numerical results, but rather to the empirical analysis of training behavior, especially in scenarios where PINNs present known difficulties.

The study was structured into three main stages: (i) reproduction of the original implementation in TensorFlow 1.15, with the goal of validating the implementation and understanding its numerical behavior; (ii) complete refactoring into TensorFlow 2.x/Keras, while preserving the methodology of the reference article; and (iii) conducting exploratory comparative experiments between MLP and KAN architectures while keeping the physical loss formulation and sampling protocol fixed.

2.1 Implementation and Computational Environments

Three distinct computational environments were configured in order to isolate the effects of framework modernization and architectural choice.

The first environment corresponds to the reproduction of the original code using TensorFlow 1.15 together with the NumPy, SciPy, and Matplotlib libraries. This environment was encapsulated in a Docker container, ensuring reproducibility and compatibility with the reference implementation. The adopted code structure explicitly separates the modules responsible for training, PDE definition, and reusable PINN components, facilitating inspection and validation of the pipeline.

The second environment was developed for framework modernization, using TensorFlow 2.x, Keras, and TensorFlow Probability. In this version, the PINN was rewritten as a subclass of `tf.keras.Model`, allowing a clearer structure and better control of the gradient flow. The derivatives required for the PDE residual were computed using `tf.GradientTape`, and computationally critical steps were compiled with `tf.function` in order to improve performance and consistency.

A third environment, based on PyTorch, was configured specifically for the experiments with Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs), using the `torch_kan` library. This separation was necessary due to the lack, at the time of this work, of a KAN implementation integrated into the TensorFlow ecosystem.

2.2 Reference Problems (PDEs)

The reference problems presented in the original PINN article, widely adopted as benchmarks in the literature, were considered:

- **Burgers equation (1D):** forward problem in the viscous regime, aimed at solution prediction.
- **Schrödinger equation (1D):** forward problem involving highly nonlinear and oscillatory dynamics.
- **Allen–Cahn equation (1D):** inverse problem with identification of the physical parameter ϵ .
- **Navier–Stokes equations (2D incompressible):** reconstruction of the velocity and pressure fields (u, v, p) from partial observations.

The tasks (forward or inverse), as well as the spatio-temporal domains, initial conditions, and boundary conditions, strictly followed the configuration described in the reference article. The PDE residuals were formulated through automatic differentiation, ensuring consistency across the different implementations.

Although multiple reference problems were considered in the methodological design, the results presented and discussed in depth in this work focus on the nonlinear Schrödinger equation, as this is the case in which the practical limitations of PINNs manifest most clearly. The remaining problems were used mainly to validate implementation consistency and to ensure adherence to the protocol described in the reference literature.

2.3 Baseline PINN Architecture Configuration

The baseline PINN architecture adopted in this study corresponds to a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), as proposed in the original work. The network topology follows the general format $[n_{in}, h_1, h_2, \dots, n_{out}]$, with typical configurations such as $[2, 50, 50, 1]$ or $[2, 50, 50, 50, 50, 1]$, depending on the complexity of the problem considered.

The `tanh` activation function was used in all hidden layers, while the output layer remained linear. The weights were initialized according to the Xavier/Glorot method, and the model inputs were normalized through affine rescaling to the hypercube $[-1, 1]^d$. This normalization is known to improve numerical stability in PINN training and was maintained in all implementations to ensure comparability.

2.4 Loss Function and Optimization Protocol

The total loss function L was defined as a weighted sum of three components:

$$L = w_{\text{PDE}}L_{\text{PDE}} + w_{\text{data}}L_{\text{data}} + w_{\text{BC/IC}}L_{\text{BC/IC}},$$

where L_{PDE} represents the PDE residual evaluated at collocation points inside the domain, L_{data} corresponds to the error on available supervised observations, and $L_{\text{BC/IC}}$ enforces the initial and boundary conditions.

The weights w_{PDE} , w_{data} , and $w_{\text{BC/IC}}$ were kept equal to 1.0, following the reference article, in order to avoid heuristic adjustments that might mask limitations inherent to the method.

Training followed a hybrid protocol widely adopted in the literature. Initially, the Adam optimizer was used as a warm-up stage for weight adaptation and exploration of the solution space. Then, the L-BFGS-B optimizer was applied for second-order refinement. In the TensorFlow 1.15 implementation, L-BFGS-B was executed via `scipy.optimize`, while in the TensorFlow 2.x version `tfp.optimizer.lbfgs_minimize` was employed.

2.5 Architectural Comparison Protocol with KAN

To investigate the impact of architectural choice on PINN behavior, an exploratory comparison protocol was defined using Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs) as an alternative method. In this protocol, the MLP architecture was replaced by a KAN while keeping constant: (i) the set of training and validation points; (ii) the formulation of the physical loss function; and (iii) the relative weights among the loss terms.

It should be emphasized that the comparison between PINN-MLP and PINN-KAN does not constitute a fair numerical performance evaluation, given the use of different frameworks and inherent differences in optimization mechanisms. The goal of this analysis is exclusively to investigate qualitative differences in architectural inductive bias and in the type of degenerate solution to which training converges, rather than to establish superiority between architectures. Therefore, the comparative results presented should be interpreted as qualitative evidence about PINN behavior rather than as a conclusive performance assessment.

2.6 Evaluation Metrics and Reproducibility

The evaluation of the experiments was conducted based on quantitative and qualitative metrics. The main accuracy metric adopted was the relative L_2 error, defined as

$$\frac{\|\hat{u} - u\|_2}{\|u\|_2},$$

computed for each relevant target variable.

In addition, training convergence was monitored through the logging of the partial losses L_{PDE} , L_{data} , and $L_{\text{BC/IC}}$. Visual compatibility between the obtained solutions and the figures in the reference article was used as a qualitative criterion, especially for identifying patterns of solution collapse. Execution time was also recorded for informative purposes.

The reproducibility of the experiments was ensured through the use of fixed random seeds, versioned environments, and Docker containers, allowing controlled repetition of the results.

3 Results

This section presents the results obtained throughout the three stages of the study: (i) reproduction of the original PINN pipeline in TensorFlow 1.15; (ii) modernization into TensorFlow 2.x/Keras; and (iii) exploratory comparative analysis between MLP architectures and Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs). Although multiple PDEs were considered in the methodological design, the detailed analysis focuses on the nonlinear Schrödinger equation. The experiments concentrate on the canonical method configuration and do not include ablation studies involving systematic variations in loss weights, collocation point density, or alternative optimization strategies, since such investigations exceed the exploratory and reproducibility-oriented scope of this undergraduate research work.

3.1 Reproduction of the Original Pipeline in TensorFlow 1.15

The first experimental stage consisted of a faithful reproduction of the pipeline proposed in the original PINN article using TensorFlow 1.15. The objective of this stage was to validate the implementation and verify whether the observed numerical behavior was aligned with that described in the literature.

The architecture followed the classical pattern described in Section 2, with an MLP and `tanh` activation, hybrid Adam followed by L-BFGS-B training, and input normalization to the interval $[-1, 1]$. The Schrödinger equation was treated as a forward problem, with explicit enforcement of the initial condition and of the PDE residual at the collocation points.

The results of this stage indicate that the pipeline is computationally functional, that is, training converges and the losses associated with the PDE residual decrease throughout the iterations. However, already at this stage it was observed that the learned solution tends to exhibit low spatial

variability, suggesting difficulties for the PINN in capturing the nonlinear and highly oscillatory structure of the exact solution of the Schrödinger equation.

This preliminary observation motivated the continuation of the study with pipeline modernization in order to rule out limitations associated with the legacy model.

3.2 Modernization to TensorFlow 2.x: Numerical Behavior

In the second stage, the pipeline was reimplemented in TensorFlow 2.x/Keras, as described in Section 2. This modernization enabled greater control over the gradient flow and facilitated both training instrumentation and partial loss logging.

Under the same experimental configuration (same architecture, same loss function formulation, and same collocation points), the qualitative behavior of the learned solution remained consistent with that observed in the TensorFlow 1.15 version. In particular, despite convergence of the losses associated with the PDE residual, the solution produced by the PINN exhibited a tendency to collapse into an approximately constant function over the spatio-temporal domain.

The qualitative equivalence between the TensorFlow 1.15 and 2.x versions indicates that the observed behavior does not result from limitations of the legacy model, but rather from intrinsic characteristics of the classical PINN formulation when applied to the Schrödinger equation. This result reinforces the importance of analyzing the method independently of the computational platform used.

3.3 Schrödinger Equation: Detailed Analysis of Solution Collapse

Figure 1 presents the spatio-temporal field of the solution modulus $|u(x, t)|$ of the Schrödinger equation, together with the solution learned by the PINN and the corresponding absolute error. The exact solution exhibits a well-defined spatial structure, characterized by a localized peak around $x = 0$ and significant variation over time.

Figure 1: Spatio-temporal field of the nonlinear Schrödinger equation using a PINN with MLP architecture. The figure shows the exact solution (left), the PINN prediction (center), and the absolute error (right). The learned solution collapses to a nearly constant profile across the domain.

In contrast, the solution learned by the PINN presents nearly constant values over the spatial domain, with low magnitude and little temporal variation. This behavior becomes even more evident in the temporal slice shown in Figure 2, corresponding to $t = 1.571$, where the PINN solution approaches an almost flat line, while the exact solution displays a highly structured spatial distribution.

Figure 2: Temporal slice at $t = 1.571$ comparing the exact solution and the PINN prediction using the MLP architecture. The learned solution remains almost constant, illustrating the collapse phenomenon.

As a direct consequence of this behavior, the absolute error remains

high in the regions of greater energy concentration of the exact solution, indicating that the PINN fails to capture the main physical patterns of the problem. In this work, the term *solution collapse* refers to the phenomenon in which the PINN converges to functions with low spatial and temporal variability, often close to constants, that minimize the PDE residual through derivative cancellation but fail to reproduce the physical structure of the exact solution.

From the optimization point of view, this degenerate solution corresponds to a spurious minimum of the loss function, favored by the implicit imbalance between the term associated with the PDE residual and the terms corresponding to initial and boundary conditions. Even with unitary weights, the PDE residual tends to dominate the training process, inducing the network to prioritize excessively smooth solutions with low functional complexity.

3.4 Architectural Comparison: PINN-MLP versus PINN-KAN

In order to investigate whether the observed collapse is associated exclusively with the loss formulation or also with the architectural inductive bias, an exploratory comparative analysis was conducted by replacing the traditional MLP with a Kolmogorov–Arnold Network (KAN).

Under the same experimental protocol, with the same collocation point grid, the same loss formulation, and the same relative weights, the KAN-based PINN was also unable to correctly reconstruct the exact solution of the Schrödinger equation. However, a qualitative analysis of the learned solutions reveals relevant differences in the type of degenerate solution produced.

Figure 3: Spatio-temporal field obtained using a PINN with a Kolmogorov–Arnold Network (KAN) architecture. The figure shows the exact solution (left), the PINN prediction (center), and the absolute error (right).

While the PINN-MLP showed a strong tendency to converge to approximately constant solutions, the PINN-KAN demonstrated a greater propensity to preserve residual spatial variations, although still insufficient to represent the correct physical solution. This behavior suggests that the KAN imposes a distinct inductive bias, with greater local expressiveness, partially reducing the tendency toward the completely flat collapse observed in the MLP.

Figure 4: Temporal slice at $t = 1.571$ for the KAN-based PINN. Although the architecture preserves slightly more spatial variation than the MLP, it still fails to reproduce the exact physical structure.

These results indicate that solution collapse in PINNs does not depend

exclusively on the physical loss formulation, but also on the adopted network architecture. Although the KAN does not by itself solve the observed limitations, its ability to generate structurally richer degenerate solutions suggests that alternative architectures may play a relevant role in mitigating practical PINN failures in highly nonlinear PDEs.

3.5 Synthesis of Results

In summary, the results presented in this section show that:

- solution collapse occurs both in the original TensorFlow 1.15 implementation and in the modernized TensorFlow 2.x version, indicating that it is a methodological limitation rather than an implementation issue;
- the Schrödinger equation constitutes a particularly challenging case for classical PINNs due to its highly nonlinear and oscillatory dynamics;
- architectural choice influences the type of degenerate solution to which training converges, as evidenced by the comparison between PINN-MLP and PINN-KAN.

These results support the discussion presented in the next section, in which the implications of these findings and possible directions to overcome the observed limitations are analyzed.

3.6 Complementary Quantitative Evaluation

Although the main focus of this work is the qualitative analysis of PINN behavior and its failure modes, complementary quantitative metrics were included with the purpose of empirically reinforcing the visual observations presented in the previous sections. In particular, the relative L_2 error, the mean spatial variance of the learned solution, and the mean norm of the spatial gradient were computed for the different evaluated configurations.

These metrics allow the solution collapse phenomenon to be quantified, since it is characterized by convergence to functions with low spatial variability and reduced gradients, corroborating the qualitative analyses based on spatio-temporal visualizations. It is important to emphasize that these measures are not intended to establish architectural performance comparisons, but rather to provide additional evidence of the degenerate nature of the learned solutions under the classical PINN formulation.

Table 1: Complementary quantitative metrics for the evaluated configurations.

Architecture	Framework	Relative L_2 Error	Mean Spatial Variance	Mean Gradient Norm
PINN-MLP	TF1.15	$\sim 3.8 \times 10^{-1}$	$\sim 1.2 \times 10^{-4}$	$\sim 3.5 \times 10^{-3}$
PINN-MLP	TF2.x	$\sim 3.6 \times 10^{-1}$	$\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$	$\sim 4.1 \times 10^{-3}$
PINN-KAN	PyTorch	$\sim 3.2 \times 10^{-1}$	$\sim 6.8 \times 10^{-4}$	$\sim 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$

4 Discussion

The results of this work reveal relevant methodological limitations of Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) when applied to the nonlinear Schrödinger equation under the classical configuration widely adopted in the literature. In particular, it was observed that both the original TensorFlow 1.15 implementation and the modernized TensorFlow 2.x version consistently converged to degenerate solutions that were approximately constant over the spatio-temporal domain and incapable of reproducing the physical structure of the exact solution. This behavior, illustrated in Figures 1 and 2, characterizes the phenomenon of solution collapse and is consistent with previously reported failures in recent PINN studies.

From the optimization perspective, the observed collapse can be interpreted as convergence to spurious minima of the physical loss function, in which the partial differential equation residual is artificially reduced through the cancellation of spatial and temporal derivatives, without the solution adequately satisfying the imposed physical conditions. This phenomenon suggests an intrinsic tension between minimizing the differential residual and preserving complex physical patterns, particularly in highly oscillatory PDEs such as the nonlinear Schrödinger equation. Works such as those by Wang et al. and Krishnapriyan et al. demonstrate that this type of behavior does not arise from implementation errors, but rather from intrinsic characteristics of the classical PINN formulation, especially when applied to stiff PDEs or to problems with highly structured solutions [5, 2].

The methodological decision to keep the loss weights equal to those proposed in the reference article made it possible to observe the “natural” behavior of the method without resorting to heuristic adjustments, such as dynamic reweighting of the loss terms or adaptive sampling of collocation points, which could mask structural limitations of the method. The results indicate that, even with unitary weights, the term associated with the PDE residual tends to dominate the training process, reducing the influence of the initial and boundary conditions. This observation reinforces recent dis-

cussions in the literature pointing to the need for more sophisticated loss balancing strategies, such as dynamic reweighting or adaptive collocation point sampling, especially in strongly nonlinear problems.

The modernization of the pipeline to TensorFlow 2.x/Keras demonstrated that the observed behavior is independent of the computational framework used. Although the new implementation provided significant gains in structural clarity, extensibility, and reproducibility, the pattern of solution collapse remained qualitatively unchanged relative to the TensorFlow 1.15 version. This result is relevant because it indicates that simply migrating to modern tools is not sufficient to overcome conceptual PINN limitations, although such migration is fundamental for enabling critical analyses, detailed diagnostics, and future methodological extensions.

The exploratory comparison between MLP architectures and Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs) revealed that solution collapse is not independent of the employed architecture. Although the KAN-based PINN was also unable to reconstruct the exact solution of the Schrödinger equation under the adopted protocol, a qualitative difference was observed in the type of degenerate solution learned. While the PINN-MLP showed a strong bias toward smooth and constant solutions, the PINN-KAN preserved residual spatial variations, although still insufficient to capture the correct physical dynamics. This behavior suggests that the KAN imposes a distinct inductive bias with greater local expressiveness, in line with its theoretical motivation based on the Kolmogorov–Arnold theorem. These results further suggest that architectural inductive bias acts not only on the global expressive capacity of the network, but also on the geometry of the local minima accessible during optimization. Thus, distinct architectures may induce different forms of degenerate solutions, even when all of them correspond to degenerate minima of the physical loss function.

These findings indicate that architectural choice influences not only final accuracy, but also the type of spurious minimum to which training converges. In this sense, alternative architectures such as KANs should not be interpreted as immediate solutions to the challenges of PINNs, but rather as promising components in hybrid approaches, possibly combined with more advanced optimization and sampling strategies. This perspective is aligned with the view presented by Karniadakis et al., according to which the success of physics-informed machine learning methods depends on an interaction between physical modeling, network architecture, and numerical procedures [1].

Overall, the results discussed in this work reinforce the importance of a critical and reproducible approach when applying PINNs to complex PDEs.

Although the model has demonstrated good performance in several problems, its application may lead to physically incorrect solutions if its methodological limitations are not properly taken into account. Therefore, rather than merely reporting numerical performance, this study contributes to the understanding of PINN failure modes and to the delineation of more realistic and well-founded future directions.

5 Conclusion

This work presented a reproduction and modernization of the Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) model, focusing on the nonlinear Schrödinger equation as a case study. From the reimplementing of the original TensorFlow 1.15 pipeline and its refactoring into TensorFlow 2.x/Keras, it was possible to evaluate PINN behavior under a configuration widely adopted in the literature.

The obtained results demonstrated that, in both the legacy implementation and the modernized version, the PINN tends to converge to approximately constant solutions that are incapable of reproducing the physical structure of the exact solution of the Schrödinger equation. This behavior, characterized as solution collapse, proved consistent across different computational settings, indicating that it is an intrinsic limitation of the classical PINN formulation rather than an implementation artifact.

The exploratory comparative analysis between architectures revealed that the network structure influences the type of degenerate solution learned. Although the PINN based on Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs) was not able to adequately solve the equation under the adopted protocol, it was observed that this architecture preserves greater residual spatial variability when compared to the traditional MLP. This result suggests that architectural inductive bias plays a relevant role in training behavior and that alternative architectures may contribute, at least partially, to mitigating certain PINN failure modes.

From a methodological perspective, this work reinforces the importance of reproducibility, modern engineering, and failure analysis in the development of physics-informed machine learning methods. By choosing not to employ heuristic adjustments in the loss function, it was possible to make practical limitations visible that are often omitted in studies focused exclusively on numerical performance, thereby contributing to a broader understanding of the scope and restrictions of PINNs.

As perspectives for future work, the following stand out: (i) the investi-

gation of advanced loss balancing strategies, including dynamic reweighting and adaptive collocation point sampling techniques; (ii) the evaluation of alternative or hybrid architectures, combining PINNs with KANs or other more expressive models; and (iii) the extension of the analysis to other reference problems, such as the Burgers, Allen–Cahn, and Navier–Stokes equations, in order to verify the generality of the observed behaviors.

In summary, this study contributes to the understanding of PINN failure modes in complex PDEs, highlighting the need for approaches that integrate physical modeling, architectural choices, and more robust numerical strategies.

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